

HIERARCHALLY MICROSTRUCTURED FIBROUS COMPOSITE SCAFFOLDS AS BONE ECM ANALOGUE

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SUMMARY

Three-dimensional porous composite scaffolds based on poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), were fabricated through the combination of a filament winding technique and a phase inversion/salt leaching process. The balance between chemical composition and spatial organization of reinforcement systems allows attaining an optimal compromise between mechanical response and bioactive potential to reproduce the bone mECM features.

Keywords: ECM, Composite, fibre reinforcement, porosity, mechanical response,

INTRODUCTION

In the natural bone tissue, the ability to sustain characteristic loads is guaranteed either by a tailored hierarchical structure at the micrometer and sub-micrometer scale, and either by a well defined chemical composition. In this context, programmed biomechanical properties need to be satisfied since the load bearing function has to be transferred from the engineered material to the growing of the mineralized extracellular matrix (mECM) [1]. In detail, bone tissue is organized into microstructural composites based on the interdigitation of collagen – the most prevalent biopolymer in the body – and an inorganic substance composed of apatitic mineral crystals. The high complexity degree of intrinsic properties of the natural tissues imposes the need to define appropriate strategies for the design of 3-D scaffolds with tailored properties, adapted to be effective in tissue engineering applications.

In this context, scaffold design to repair hard tissues such as bone may be complex. Indeed, the primary function of a bone substitute has to be the capability of supporting loads adequately. In that case, the scaffold should not only be a highly porous structure, able to guide novel tissue formation in 3-D space, but also it should have sufficient mechanical strength to offer adequate structural support. Furthermore, it should be able to stimulate new bone growth, resulting, finally, in native bone tissue with no trace of the scaffold. Moving towards the current standing of biomaterials science and technology, the challenging way to satisfy the compelling multifunctional needs and extend material property combinations relies on the development of composite materials made of degradable and partially degradable materials [2].

To date, the employment of not degradable composite materials was a valid solution to bone replacement, by achieving the ideal balance between strength and toughness due to the improvement of specific characteristics of the composite compared to its separate

components. However, the need of scaffold materials to be porous, biocompatible and biodegradable, and to exhibit a degradation or resorption rate similar to the rate of tissue replacement, is often in conflict with the possession of adequate mechanical properties able to match those of the tissues at the implantation site. Contrariwise, the employment of biodegradable composites may represent an innovative solution for tissue regeneration. Indeed, they may hinder the stress-shielding phenomena associated with the use of traditional rigid metal-based implants. Meanwhile, the continuous degradation of the implant causes a gradual load transfer to the healing tissue, preventing the stress-shielding atrophy with the stimulation of the healing and the bone remodelling.

This work is aimed at focusing the preparation strategies of composite scaffolds characterized by tailored degradation properties, coupled with controlled mechanical response, in order to guarantee the achievement of the long-term success of a tissue engineered construct. In this work, novel composite scaffolds were proposed by the combined use of two reinforcement systems in different forms – particles and long fibres – to optimize the final mechanical response of the scaffold. Three dimensional porous PCL-based composite scaffolds, tubular in shape, were prepared by the combination of the filament winding technique and a phase inversion/salt leaching process [3]. The employment of highly biocompatible and bioresorbable PCL and PLA assures the maintenance of sufficient physical and mechanical properties for at least six months before their degradation. The integration of a solid porogen (i.e. sodium chloride crystals) within a 3-D polymer matrix enables creation of an interconnected pore network with well-defined pore sizes and shapes. Finally, to extend the biological performance of synthetic materials, a promising strategy consists of chemically or physically encoding some bioactive cues into micro-structured platforms. Indeed, tissue regeneration, whenever it occurs in response to physiological conditions or to trauma, is a result of a complex cascade of events. Composite scaffolds may represent the new frontiers for developing smart materials able to regulate these events coordinating them in spatial and temporal modalities through the guide offered by biophysical and biochemical signals, naturally triggered by the extracellular microenvironment.

Here, different bioactive signals were physically incorporated into the polymer matrix. In the last years, several authors [4][5] proposed the addition of solid signals consisting of micrometric or nanometric hydroxyapatite (HA) rigid particles within polymer matrix to improve the osteoconductivity of the composite. In this case, tri-calcium phosphate (α -TCP) powder has been used because of its ability to precipitate in calcium-deficient hydroxyapatite (CDHA) form, largely recognized by the host tissue as being similar to natural bone apatite [6]. Moreover, chemical modification of haluronan, consisting of the partial or total esterification of the carboxyl groups of the haluronic acid (HYAFF) have been chosen to activate specific biological properties [7]. In particular, the HYAFF11 used in this work, shows a recognized capability of favouring or, conversely, inhibiting the adhesion of certain cell types such as chondrocytes and mesenchymal stem cells (MSCs) which may be successfully used for bone tissue engineering.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The preparation of the PCL based composite scaffolds is graphically described in *Figure 1*. Briefly, Poly(3-caprolactone) pellets were dissolved in N,N-

dimethylacetamide 20% w/w by stirring for about 3 h at 58 °C. NaCl 300–500 nm-sized particles were added to the PCL matrix (weight ratio: 9/1) to get a homogeneous mixture. Fibre-reinforced composite structures were obtained by the integration of PLLA fibres prepared by filament winding technique.

The filament winding machine (mod. AS LAB 101 – T.EL.MEC, Italy) consists of a rotating mandrel and a fibre dispensing head moving along the length of the mandrel (*Figure 2*). The head motion which is synchronized with the mandrel rotation enables to define the angle of the fibre with respect to the mandrel axis, so that helical plies optimized to handle expected loads can be laid down. Before the winding on the mandrel, the single fibre has to go across a resin bath: the matrix viscosity and the fibre shear rate play a main role on the fibre-to-matrix adhesion. Moreover, the machine parameters (i.e. winding pitch, winding angle) may be set in order to get different winding patterns as required. In the specific case, PLLA fibres impregnated with the PCL-based mixture were rotated by using a winding angle of 45° and a winding pitch of 500 mm, respectively, on Teflon coated steel mandrel for five fibre-cycle. The solvent was extracted from the matrix by ethanol dipping (35 ml for gram of composite) for 24 h. Then, samples were totally immersed in bi-distilled water for 7 days to leach out salt and any other contaminants. Finally, the porous material was dried under hood at room temperature for 6 h to obtain the final sample ready to use.

The addition of bioactive factors (tri-calcium phosphates and Hyaff11) was performed directly to the polymer solution before the winding procedure. In detail, a mixture of calcium phosphate powders (98 wt.% α -TCP, 2% HA – kindly supplied by Universitat Polytechnica de Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain) with different volume fractions (13, 20 and 26%) and 20%wt of Hyaff11 were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bone tissue is as an organic/inorganic composite with a hierarchical organization of single material phases: mineral HA with high elastic modulus contributes significantly to the bone stiffness, whereas assembled collagen in fibril bundles softens the rigidity of the ceramic phase, improving the composite toughness. Starting from this point of view, a new generation of composite materials may be advantageously proposed to develop hybrid materials which combine the strength and stiffness of an inorganic compound, and the flexibility, toughness and resorbability of an organic phase. In particular, the ambitious aim of this work consists in designing a complex composite system using biocompatible materials able to promote natural body healing, which is able to degrade through multi-scale kinetics after implantation, and contain biologically active phases and/or molecules, able to stimulate the regenerative tissue growth in order to mimic the morphological and microstructural properties of bone tissue.

Here, the proposed approach based on the preparation of composite scaffolds by the combination of a filament winding technique with the traditional phase inversion/salt leaching method enabled the production of 3-D structures which offer a valid compromise between porosity and functional requirements. Because of their chemical and structural similarities, PCL and PLA, being derived from the family of poly(α -hydroxyesters), degrade in similar fashion through ester hydrolysis processes and decarboxylation from the chain ends, assuring their complete removal by natural pathways. However, different degradation kinetics may occur, depending on specific

interatomic and intermolecular bonding, which induces a different susceptibility to hydrolytic attack and breakdown with different effects on the final degradation behaviour [8]. As a consequence, a multi-scale degradable systems may be efficaciously developed by assembling different phases with time-controlled degradation.

Starting from this idea, fibre-reinforced composite scaffolds were fabricated by the integration of hydrophilic PLA continuous fibres into an hydrophobic PCL matrix as scaffolds for bone regeneration [3]. In proposed systems, the long-term degradation of PCL matrix following a two-step mechanism – i.e. random hydrolytic ester cleavage and weight loss through the diffusion of oligomeric species from the bulk – guarantees a substrate with mechanical properties and support function until tissue regeneration has been accomplished [9]. Meanwhile, PLLA fibre bundles, which are strictly ordered by helicoidal arrangement inside the scaffold due to their degradation faster than the PCL matrix, may promote the formation of preferential channels to guide cell migration.

In these fibrous composites, degradation preferentially occurs at the fibre-polymer interface, resulting in a degradation rate higher than the material alone. Usually, characteristic degradation rate of composites is too high and not totally adequate for clinical applications such as bone fracture fixation which require a strength retention in the long term (i.e few weeks up to several months). However, continuous fibre reinforced composite made of two interconnecting phases which better mimic the bone structural organization, assures a strong mechanical interlocking between two phases which offers the support for retaining some of its properties if breakdown occurs at the interface. This difficulty imposed an accurate design of composite materials through the optimization of the adhesion between matrix and reinforcement system by selecting an optimal fibre matrix ratios and winding parameter configuration. In this direction, semi-empirical modelling based on weight measurements supported by simple geometrical considerations (i.e, assumption of helical organization of fibres into the tubular scaffold) enabled to predict the exact composition of the phases into the composite system. Besides, the definition of an interfacial bonding able to promote a more rapid diffusion of fluids at the matrix/fibre interface but also capable to not limit the mechanical strength and fatigue, offers the optimal compromise condition for improving the final composite properties. However, the time evolution of degradation is strictly correlated to the porosity which influence the flow of biological media into the polymer network, drastically accelerating the chemical interaction with the structure.

In the proposed systems, a bimodal porosity was evidenced by quantitative investigation, using mercury intrusion porosimetry supported by microCT analysis (*Figure 3*). The mercury intrusion technique enabled a quantification of the interconnected porosity, giving a value of ca. 80%. The porosity showed two ranges of pore size, namely micropores with mean diameter of 2.24 μm and macropores with diameters over 200 μm . Macropores are suitable for the accommodation of osteoblast and undifferentiated bone mesenchymal stem cells, while the micropores offers interconnection bridges between adjacent macropores, able to promote the nutrient and metabolite exchange improving the structural interconnectivity. Preliminary evaluation of the attachment and cell proliferation of human bone cells (marrow stromal cells, trabecular osteoblasts) cells confirmed the main role of scaffolds morphology on the cell/material interaction adumbrating the potential active role in vivo of proposed composite systems [3].

However, several lacks in biological response and mechanical behaviour of synthetic polymers prevent the right mimicking of bone tissue functionalities, by imposing the addition of further materials phases like ceramic particles. For instance, it is well-known that HA addition to the plain polymer strongly enhances the mechanical performances of the PCL scaffold by exhibiting the hardening function offered by the fine dispersion of particles inside the polymer matrix of PCL which shows a significant increase of the mechanical resistance and up to a three-fold increase in the elastic modulus [3]. However, the potential of rigid particles as reinforcement system is strongly conditioned by their reactivity in biological environment [10].

On the basis of promising results of recent studies of hard mineralized tissues [11], it has been proposed the coupling of degradable polymers with reactive calcium phosphates for the bone regeneration. In particular, use of calcium phosphates is recommended for their ability to buffer the intermediate acidic products of the degradation of the polymeric phase, reducing the risk of inflammatory responses in the body [12]. In the presence of water, α -TCP hydrolyses through a dissolution precipitation reaction, giving rise to the formation of an entangled network of CDHA crystals, which are close to the mineral component of bone from a structural point of view [13]. In the proposed scaffolds, the hydrolysis reaction occurs during the salt leaching step. The micropore network, formed during the previous phase inversion, supports the water diffusion, accelerating the sodium chloride crystal dissolution and promoting the interaction with the reactive ceramic particles. Furthermore, the highly ordered interfacial interactions which occur between the organized pre-tensed continuous fibres and the growing needle-like crystals during the leaching result in a progressive increase in the stiffness of the final composite scaffolds, up to the values necessary to mimic the mechanical behaviour of trabecular bone. Typical σ - ϵ curve at low deformations along the toe region shows compressive moduli which vary from 0.485 ± 0.041 to 2.211 ± 0.242 MPa as a function of the inorganic phase amount (*Figure 4*).

In order to prevent some limitations of polymers in terms of acute inflammatory phenomena as evidenced by “in vivo” experiments [14], semi-synthetic materials like HYAFF formulations obtained by chemical modification of purified hyaluronan may be used in combination with them. In our case, the addition of HYAFF 11 cues into the PLLA fibre reinforced PCL matrix concur to obtain porous scaffolds with tailored microstructure and degradation properties. Accordingly with the features of other systems previously reported, the porous architecture is still characterized by a well-interconnected network of macropores from 100 to 200 μ m in size, bridged by micropores ranging from 0.1 to 10 micrometers due to the combined effect of phase inversion and salt leaching. It has been remarked a drastic reduction of the structural order of the scaffold due to a less homogeneous micro and macropore size distributions which may be explained by volumetric shrinkage phenomena interesting the hydrogel-like phase. Preliminary studies are oriented to functionalize the composite scaffolds by morphogenic signals (i.e, BMP-7) in order to guide the cell recruitment into the scaffold. In an effort to recapitulate the native microenvironment that surrounds cells, namely synthetic extracellular matrix (ECM), the hydrogel-like phases should promote the entrapment of molecular signals within the scaffold to assure a controlled release in the implant defects.

CONCLUSION

Engineering osseous tissue with cells and a synthetic extracellular matrix is an alternative approach to the established practice of transplantation of harvested tissues. Degradable composite scaffolds, prepared by combining a filament winding technique with a phase inversion/salt leaching method, represents a valid solution to achieving adequate porosity requirements while providing adequate support in load-bearing applications. The proposed novel process for preparing fibre-reinforced composite scaffolds is as quick and versatile as conventional technologies. The integration of biodegradable PLA fibres into the polymer matrix guarantees a mechanical response which is ideal for maintaining the spaces required for cellular in-growth and matrix production. Furthermore, the addition of bioactive calcium phosphates particles, through a hardening reaction, generates needle-like CDHA crystals, which interact with the fibre-reinforced polymeric matrix. The further addition of hydrogel-like phases may be positively contribute to the nutrient transport as well as the specific factor release finely mimicking the ECM functionalities.

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FIGURES

Figure 1:
Scheme of the preparation of the composite.

Figure 2:
Filament winding procedure to integrate PLLA fibre into salt-added polymer matrix

Mercury intrusion

Bi-modal porosity

2D

3D

Micro-CT

Pore spatial distribution

Figure 3:
Porosity evaluation by mercury intrusion porosimetry and MicroCT (2-D and 3-D reconstruction)

Figure 4:
Effect of α -TCP amount on morphology and mechanical response.